

AN INTRINSIC FLAW MODEL FOR PREDICTION OF FLAW DENSITY AND DISTRIBUTION WITH MACHINING TOOL VELOCITY

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A distribution of intrinsic flaw lengths is calculated from experimental data for the strength and failure site variability of unnotched 10-degree off-axis specimens. The distribution of intrinsic flaw lengths is then used with the strength variability of the unnotched and of open-hole specimens to determine the flaw density at each hole-size. The flaw density is shown to be related to the fabrication machining speed suggesting machining damage as a mechanism for the hole-size dependence of the flaw density. Then the distribution of intrinsic flaw lengths and the flaw density can be used to predict the mean strength of open-hole 10-degree off-axis specimens as a function of machine tool velocity

1 General Introduction

The concept of the intrinsic flaw was first introduced by Waddoups [1], where fracture mechanics concepts were used to guide the prediction of the hole-size effect in multi-axial laminates – namely that the laminate notched strength varies significantly with the absolute hole size even for the plate of infinite extent. Waddoups postulated existence of an “intense energy region” of length a at the edges of the circular hole and perpendicular to the tensile loading axis for orthotropic laminates. Using the Bowie solution [2] for the Mode I stress intensity factor for a crack extending perpendicular to the loading direction from the edge of a circular hole of radius, R in an isotropic material:

$$K_I = \sigma_\infty \sqrt{\pi a} f\left(\frac{a}{R}\right) \quad (1)$$

where the function, $f(a/R)$, is known, he determined the “length of the characteristic dimension” from the strength of an unnotched specimen, σ_0 , and a single notched specimen, σ_N , with hole-radius, R . The ratio of the unnotched strength to the notched

strength yielded $f(a/R)$ from which a could be determined:

$$\frac{\sigma_0}{\sigma_N} = f\left(\frac{a}{R}\right) \rightarrow a \quad (2)$$

By assuming a constant characteristic length, a , prediction of the hole-size effect follows from Eqn. 2.

In the present work, the authors build upon the Waddoups’ approach, but focus on the unidirectional, off-axis specimen of specified aspect ratio (length-to-width) and containing circular hole at the geometric center of the specimen. The shear coupling characteristics of the off-axis tensile specimen bring a level of anisotropy to this problem not previously examined with a fracture mechanics approach. Shear coupling also introduces a mixed-mode fracture condition to the open-hole fracture process. Further, location of the site of the flaw or crack along the perimeter of the hole is not known prior to failure for the off-axis tensile specimen. These issues are considered in the present work.

The intrinsic flaw, shown in Fig. 1, is defined as a through-thickness, planar crack extending in the fiber direction from the failure initiation site to a length, a . The simple crack geometry is consistent with the physical observation that the fracture surface extends through the thickness of the specimen and is parallel to the fiber direction. Fracture mechanics is used to analyze failure since self-similar crack propagation is observed in all tests. In the case of the unnotched specimen, the crack is located at the experimental site of failure initiation, taken to be the intersection of the fracture surface with the free-edge of the specimen. Stress analysis is performed to determine the local stress field magnitude at the failure site and the fracture mechanics analysis is performed with the intrinsic

flaw crack geometry to determine the critical crack size that corresponded to failure when subjected to the local stress magnitude. The length of the critical crack is then defined as the “*intrinsic flaw length*”. It is observed that the experimental strength and failure site data vary when test conditions remain unchanged. The variability in strength and failure site is used to obtain the distribution of intrinsic flaw lengths by repeating the stress analysis and fracture analysis. In this way, a probability density function of intrinsic flaw lengths for the material system under investigation is determined.

In the strength predictions for the specimens, the intrinsic flaw crack geometry and probability density function of intrinsic flaw lengths calculated from the unnotched specimens allow fracture mechanics predictions of strength variability. The strength prediction is dependent on the flaw density, the number of flaws per unit length along the free-edge. The flaw density is established by matching the predicted strength with the experimental strength. While this approach clearly provides an approach to determining the strength variability of the open-hole specimens, the authors have chosen to focus on establishment of the flaw density based on the prediction of mean strength as a first test of the approach. In strength prediction it is necessary to sample at a finite number of locations and thereby, a distance between interrogation sites along the free edge is specified. Through Monte-Carlo simulation, a fraction of interrogation sites along the specimen free-edge are assigned a flaw. The length of the flaw is determined from the probability density function of intrinsic flaw lengths. The stress analysis is again performed to determine the local stress field magnitude at each of the sample sites where the fracture analysis is performed to determine the strength. The predicted specimen strength is the minimum of the strengths at each of the interrogation sites containing a flaw. The mean strength is developed by repeating the simulation. Next, these results are compared with the actual experimental mean strength. The flaw density is determined by matching the predicted strength to the experimental strength data. This process is repeated at each hole-diameter to determine the flaw density at each hole-size.

The dependence of the flaw density on hole-size is then related to machining speed, suggesting machining-induced damage as a mechanism for the flaw density dependence on hole-size. Additionally, relating the flaw density to the machining speed allows the prediction of strength at each hole-size based the flaw density determined from the machining speed. The agreement between the predicted and experimental strength supports the machine-speed-dependence of the flaw density.

2 Experimental

Multiple 10-degree off-axis specimens were tested in tension to failure. Both unnotched specimens and specimens with a centrally-located, through-thickness circular hole were tested. The specimen geometry is shown in Fig. 2. The average specimen dimensions were: width, $W = 19$ mm, thickness, $T = 3.4$ mm, gage length between tabs, $L = 152$ mm, yielding an aspect ratio, $L/W = 8$. Circular hole-diameters for the open-hole specimens were 1.00, 1.57, 3.18, 4.76, 6.35, 7.94, 9.53 and 12.70 mm. The test matrix is shown in Table 1. Fractured unnotched specimen and fractured open-hole specimens at each hole-diameter are shown in Fig. 3(a). The fracture surface in the unnotched specimens was parallel to the fiber direction and extended from one lateral free-edge to the other through the thickness of the specimen. The failure initiation site in the unnotched specimen is taken to be the intersection of the fracture surface and the free-edge. Because the typical fracture surface was not perpendicular to the plane of the specimen, the positions of the intercepts of the failure surface with the specimen free-edges were deemed the failure sites, as indicated by arrows in Fig. 3(b). In this way, four failure sites were recorded per specimen failure, two located on each free-edge. In the open-hole specimens, the fracture surface was again parallel in the fiber direction, extended through the thickness of the specimen and intercepted the perimeter of the circular hole. An axial strain gage, positioned at the geometric center of unnotched specimens and positioned midway between the perimeter of the circular hole and the edge of the tab of open-hole specimens, provide measures of the far-field strain at failure for each specimen.

3 Calculation of Intrinsic Flaw Length

The intrinsic flaw geometry, shown in Fig. 1, defined as a through-thickness, planar crack extending in the fiber direction from the failure initiation site of length, a , is consistent with the physical observation that the fracture surface extends through the thickness of the specimen and is parallel to the fiber direction. Fracture mechanics is warranted to analyze failure given the self-similar crack propagation of the failure process. Because both Mode I and Mode II fracture mechanisms are present in the off-axis specimen due to shear-coupling, the mixed-mode fracture criterion is used in the fracture analysis:

$$\left(\frac{K_I}{K_{I,c}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{K_{II}}{K_{II,c}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (3)$$

Where K_I and K_{II} are the Mode I and Mode II stress intensity factors, defined for a center-crack of length $2a$ in an infinite sheet as:

$$\begin{aligned} K_I &= \sigma\sqrt{\pi a} \\ K_{II} &= \tau\sqrt{\pi a} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$K_{I,c}$ and $K_{II,c}$ are the Mode I and Mode II fracture toughness values. Here a is the crack length and σ and τ are the local field normal and shearing stress components, respectively. The intrinsic flaw is located at the site of failure initiation which is taken to be the intersection of the fracture surface with the free-edge of the specimen.

The Pagano-Halpin analytic elasticity solution for the off-axis coupon [3] was exercised to determine the homogenized strain field in the lamina at the failure site. Boundary conditions account for the effects of end-constraint [3] and the axial displacement is scaled to match the axial strain at failure observed by the far-field strain gage. The solution is interrogated at the observed failure site to determine the homogenized mechanical strain tensor, $(\bar{\varepsilon}_j - \bar{\alpha}_j \Delta T)$. Micromechanical enhancement (MME) [4, 5] allows dehomogenization to calculate the local micromechanical strain tensor in the matrix at the failure site. In the MME approach, the micromechanical strain tensor at a point k , $\varepsilon_i^k - \alpha_i^k \Delta T$ in a doubly-periodic representative volume element is given by the following influence function formulation:

$$\varepsilon_i^k - \alpha_i^k \Delta T = M_{ij}^k (\bar{\varepsilon}_j - \bar{\alpha}_j \Delta T) + A_i^k \Delta T \quad (5)$$

where M_{ij}^k is the influence function matrix relating the homogenized mechanical strain tensor (total strains less free thermal strains), $(\bar{\varepsilon}_j - \bar{\alpha}_j \Delta T)$, A_i^k is the thermal superposition vector, which accounts for the thermal expansion mismatch between fiber and matrix, and ΔT is the uniform temperature change, taken as -150°C , the difference between cure and room temperature. The unit cell for square-pack geometry and the k th point used in this study, which is located midway between two fibers, are shown in Fig. 4. Calculation of the micromechanical stress components, σ and τ in Eqn. 5 from the micromechanical strain tensor is accomplished through isotropic constitutive relations for the matrix material, with material properties listed in Table 2.

A fracture mechanics analysis is performed with the intrinsic flaw geometry to determine the critical crack size that corresponds to failure at the local stress magnitudes, σ and τ by substituting Eqn. 2 into Eqn. 1 and solving for a .

$$a = \left(\frac{\sigma^2 \pi}{K_{I,c}^2} + \frac{\tau^2 \pi}{K_{II,c}^2} \right)^{-1} \quad (6)$$

The length defined in Eqn. 6 is the length of the critical crack and thereby, defined as the intrinsic flaw length. As stated above, four failure sites were determined for each specimen failure and four intrinsic flaw lengths could be determined in each test. Of the four flaw lengths, the minimum is the critical crack length and is taken as the length of the flaw that would have caused failure. In this way, one flaw length was recorded per test. The stress and fracture analysis are repeated for each of the 28 unnotched specimens in order to calculate the variability in the critical crack length. In this way, a probability density function of intrinsic flaw lengths was determined.

The probability density function of the intrinsic flaw lengths calculated from the strains-to-failure and the failure sites of 28 replicate tests of the 10-degree unnotched off-axis specimen is shown in Fig. 5. The intrinsic flaw lengths in this distribution range

between 7.9 microns to 27.8 microns, with a mean intrinsic flaw length of 15.3 microns. For a carbon fiber diameter of 5 microns, the intrinsic flaws vary between 1.6 – 5.6 fiber diameters in length, and are therefore, of the same length scale as the relevant geometry at the microscale of the composite material under study.

4 Flaw Density

4.1 Determination of Flaw Density

The intrinsic flaw geometry and probability density function of intrinsic flaw lengths calculated from the unnotched specimens are next used to compare the predicted and experimental strength variability with the goal of establishing the flaw density, or number of flaws per unit length. The distance between interrogation sites along the free edge, Δs , is chosen. Here $\Delta s = 0.139$ mm/site. While this choice may appear arbitrary, it was made using the constraints of computational efficiency and appropriate resolution. Investigation sites are limited to the length along the free-edge such that the fracture surface extending from the failure site will be contained within the specimen length. For this geometry and lamina fiber orientation, the length is 44.1 mm. In this way, failure sites that would lead to grip-failures are excluded from the prediction. The fraction of interrogation sites that contain a flaw is f_{flaw} , allowing the flaw density, ρ_{flaw} to be defined as:

$$\rho_{flaw} = \frac{f_{flaw}}{\Delta s} \quad (7)$$

In a Monte-Carlo simulation, each interrogation site along the free-edge is assigned a random number, f_{site} , and at each site where, $f_{site} < f_{flaw}$, an intrinsic flaw length, a , sampled at random from the probability density function of intrinsic flaw lengths is assigned. The local stress field magnitude, σ and τ , at each site where a flaw length has been assigned is then determined. Fracture analysis with the mixed-mode fracture criterion, Eqn. 3, is carried out to determine the failure conditions at each site. The failure criterion is determined by substitution of Eqn. 4 into Eqn. 3.

$$\left(\frac{\sigma\sqrt{\pi a}}{K_{I,c}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau\sqrt{\pi a}}{K_{II,c}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (8)$$

The predicted strength of the specimen is then determined as the minimum of the strengths of the

interrogation sites where flaws were assigned. By repeating the Monte-Carlo simulation, the variability of strength can be determined. Next, the mean predicted strength is compared with the mean experimental strength. If the difference is greater than a given tolerance, the flaw density is adjusted the entire process is repeated. The flaw density is iteratively established by matching the predicted and experimental mean strengths. For the unnotched specimen, the flaw density was 0.025 flaw/mm.

The process of predicting the strength and matching the predicted strength to the experimental strength in order to determine the flaw density is repeated at each hole-diameter. In this way, the flaw density at each hole-size is established. In the case of open-hole specimens, the angular distance between interrogation sites around the perimeter of the circular hole, $\Delta\phi$ is determined by matching the arc length between interrogation sites along the perimeter of the hole, $\Delta\phi R$, where R is the radius of the hole, to the linear distance between interrogation sites along the free-edge of the unnotched specimen, $\Delta s = \Delta\phi R$. Investigating the perimeter of the circular hole is consistent with the experimental observation that the fracture surface always intersects the perimeter of the hole. The process of strength prediction by investigating sites around the perimeter of the circular hole is necessary for determination of the flaw density and is identical to the process used for strength prediction of unnotched specimens. A plane-stress, linear-elastic, finite-element analysis of the open-hole geometry specimen is performed to determine the homogenized lamina strains at the interrogation sites where a flaw is assigned. The boundary conditions, referring to the specimen geometry in Fig. 2 are, at $x = -L/2$, the axial displacement is $u = 0$, and transverse displacement is $v = 0$, and at $x = L$, the axial displacement is $u = \epsilon_x L$, and the transverse displacement is $v = 0$. The lateral edges and perimeter of the circular-hole are traction free.

The flaw density at each hole-size is shown in Fig. 6. It is observed that the flaw density decreases with hole-size and is inversely proportional to the hole-diameter in the open-hole specimens. The greatest flaw density is 4.52 flaw/mm and occurs for the 1.00 mm open-hole specimen. The least flaw density for the open-hole specimens occurs for the 9.53 mm

open-hole specimen and is 0.79 flaw/mm. The unnotched specimens exhibited the least flaw density, 0.025 flaw/mm, which was one order of magnitude less than the least flaw density in the open-hole specimens.

4.1 Relationship Between Flaw Density and Machining Speed

The flaw density may be related to the machining speed used in fabrication. The straight edges of all specimens were machined using multiple-pass cutting with a 10-inch-diameter diamond-embedded saw operating at 1,500 rpm. The circular-holes were fabricated using a diamond-tipped core drill with a tool diameter equal to the diameter of the circular-hole, operating at 12,000 rpm. The machine linear velocity, V was calculated from the product of the rotational velocity, ω and the tool diameter, D as $V = \pi\omega D$. The flaw density is shown in Fig. 7 versus the inverse of the machining speed, $1/V$ at each hole-size. The flaw density at each hole-size is observed to vary linearly with the inverse of the machining speed. This suggests machining-induced damage as a possible mechanism for the variation of flaw density with hole-size. The flaw density for the unnotched specimen is observed to not be collinear with the flaw densities of the open-hole specimens. As stated, the lateral-edges of the unnotched specimens were fabricated with a different process and tool than the edges at the perimeter of the circular-hole in the open-hole specimens. The flaw density may be predicted for each hole-size using the relationship between machining speed and flaw density and is shown in Fig. 6 for comparison with the flaw density which was determined by matching the strength at each hole-size.

4.2 Prediction of Strength

The process of predicting the mean strength of off-axis specimens follows closely the process used to establish the flaw density with the exception that iteration is not used to match the predicted strength to the experimental strength. Rather, the flaw density calculated from the tool-speed is used to predict the strength at each hole-size. The intrinsic flaw lengths calculated from the unnotched specimen are used in the prediction of strength at each hole-size. Prediction of the far-field strain-to-failure at each hole-diameter is shown in Fig. 8 and compared with the mean of the experimental far-

field strain-to-failure at each hole-diameter, where good agreement is observed for all but the unnotched specimen geometry. The agreement in the strength predictions confirms that the flaw density calculated from the tool speed may be used to accurately predict the strength of the 10 degree open-hole specimens.

5 Conclusions

An intrinsic flaw was defined as a through-thickness, planar crack extending in the fiber direction from the failure initiation site to a length, a , consistent with the physical observation that the fracture surface extended through the thickness of the specimen and was parallel to the fiber direction. In the case of the unnotched specimen, the crack was located at the experimental site of failure initiation, stress analysis was performed to determine the local stress field magnitude at the failure site and the fracture mechanics analysis was performed with the intrinsic flaw crack geometry to determine the critical crack size that corresponded to failure when subjected to the local stress magnitude. The length of the critical crack was then defined as the “*intrinsic flaw length*”. The variability in strength and failure site was used to obtain the distribution of intrinsic flaw lengths by repeating the stress analysis and fracture analysis. In this way, a probability density function of intrinsic flaw lengths for the material system under investigation was determined. The intrinsic flaws varied between 1.6 – 5.6 carbon fiber diameters in length, and are therefore, of the same length scale as the relevant geometry at the microscale of the composite material under study.

The intrinsic flaw crack geometry and probability density function of intrinsic flaw lengths calculated from the unnotched specimens provide the foundation for fracture mechanics predictions of strength based on the flaw density in the unnotched and open-hole specimens. A distance between interrogation sites along the free edge or perimeter of the circular-hole was specified and through Monte-Carlo simulation, a fraction of interrogation sites along the specimen edge were assigned a flaw. The fraction of the sites containing flaws was governed by the flaw density. The length of the flaw was determined from the probability density function of intrinsic flaw lengths. The stress analysis

was again performed to determine the local stress field magnitude at each of the sample sites where the fracture analysis was performed to determine the strength. The minimum of the strengths at each of the interrogation sites containing a flaw was the predicted specimen strength, and the mean strength was developed by repeating the simulation. These results were compared with the actual experimental mean strength and the flaw density was established by matching the predicted strength to the experimental strength data. In this way the flaw density at each hole-size was established and was observed to be inversely proportional to hole-diameter.

The flaw density at each hole-size was related to the machining speed. It was found that the flaw density varied linearly with the inverse of the machining speed. This suggests machining-induced damage as a mechanism for the dependence of flaw density on hole-size. The flaw density of the unnotched specimens, which were fabricated with a different process and cutting tool, was not collinear with the flaw density of the open-hole specimens. The strain-to-failure of the off-axis specimens was predicted using the flaw density calculated from the tool-speed. With the exception of the unnotched and 1.00 mm open-hole specimens, the strength predictions showed excellent agreement with the experimental strength, underscoring the relationship between the machining speed and the flaw density.

While it remains to be demonstrated that the intrinsic flaw methodology will be tractable in the more complex multi-axial laminate configuration, the intrinsic flaw approach provides the unique ability to treat the case of flaws in heterogeneous microstructure and located at any point along the perimeter of the circular hole. Additionally, the method considers the effect of shear-coupling and treats the case of mixed-mode fracture. In the method, we have appealed to linear superposition in that the crack imposed on the local stress field without influencing the field. Further, we have assumed a center-crack-geometry for the intrinsic flaw even though all flaw locations were restricted to the perimeter of the hole or the lateral edge. In addition, MME “dehomogenization” was used to calculate micromechanical stresses and strains at a free-surface where the periodicity of the

representative volume element concept is likely violated. However, the agreement between the experiments and predictions argue that errors arising from these simplifications are compensated by the self-consistency of the approach. Finally, it is apparent that though the intrinsic flaw method focused on the prediction of mean strength as a means to establish the flaw density of the off-axis specimen, the method may also be utilized in the prediction of strength variability as well.

6 References

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7 Tables and Figures

Table 1: Experimental specimens

Hole Diameter (mm)	Number of Specimens
Unnotched	28
1.00	2
1.59	3
3.18	2
4.76	3
6.35	42
7.94	3
9.53	2
12.70	3

Table 2: Material Properties

Property	Lamina	Matrix	Fiber
E_1 (GPa)	151	4.76	276
$E_2=E_3$ (GPa)	8.00	4.76	19.5
$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	0.32	0.37	0.28
ν_{23}	0.45	0.37	0.70
$G_{12}=G_{13}$ (GPa)	4.27	1.74	70
G_{23} (GPa)	2.73	1.74	5.74
α_1 ($10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	-0.29	64.8	-0.4
$\alpha_1=\alpha_2$ ($10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	29.3	64.8	5.6
$K_{I,c}$ ($\text{kN}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$)	61.2	56.8	---
$K_{II,c}$ ($\text{kN}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$)	248	108**	---

* Manufacturer's data sheet, ** Estimated

Fig. 1: Intrinsic flaw

Fig. 2: Specimen geometry

Fig. 3: (a) Failed unnotched and open-hole 10 degree off-axis specimens, (b) Fracture surface through the thickness of the unnotched specimen showing failure initiation sites

Fig. 4: Micromechanical unit cell and interrogation point

Fig. 5: Intrinsic flaw length in 10-degree off-axis unnotched and open-hole specimens

Fig. 6: Flaw density in 10-degree off-axis specimens determined by matching predicted strength with experimental strength and by prediction from inverse of machining speed

Fig. 7: Dependence of flaw density on the inverse of machining speed. The flaw density is determined by matching the predicted strength with the experimental strength at each hole-size.

Fig. 8: Predicted and experimental strength versus hole-size in the 10-degree off-axis specimens. The flaw density at each hole-size was predicted from the machining speed. The predicted strength is the mean of 10,000 repetitions at each hole-size.